

DEVELOPING STUDENTS' READING COMPREHENSION

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Annotation:

The aim of this article is to present the effectiveness of text and tasks on the reading achievement of language learners into the learning process. In the recent researches on pedagogy and linguistics it is highly recommended to use several reading strategies, which involves giving learners the opportunity to individually expand and deepen their language skills, as well as forming their subject position in determining their educational path. The paper reveals the essence of using authentic materials in teaching a foreign language especially improving reading skill and gives structurally-substantial characteristics; the content and methods of interacting reading strategies in reading learning process and, in general, the implementation of different technologies in the practice of the education system.

Key words: reading comprehension, reading skill, language skill, reading activities, authentic materials, active vocabulary, passive vocabulary, text and tasks.

INTRODUCTION

The process of reading has a huge impact on the formation of personality. With the help of reading in English, students enrich their active and passive vocabulary of words, form grammatical skills and there is a study of the culture of this language. One of the main problems of learning to read is the problem of selecting texts and clearly organizing work with them. Improvement of old traditional forms of education and search for new means, forms, methods, adequate to the development goals of participants in the educational process, is

the actual problem of modern education, in the aspect of which the study was carried out.

The practical significance of the research lies in the development and application in practice during pedagogical practice in exercises and different reading strategies aimed at teaching reading skills to learners in their EFL lessons. In Process and procedures part, there is explained research plan of the qualification paper including its methods, subjects, materials and equipment used in practicum as well as procedure containing different variables and data collections. Results and discussion part deal with the analysis of practical works which conducted in two months. The final reflections part contains the main conclusions of the work.

The research paper will attempt to answer the following questions in as much detail as possible:

- How can learners be motivated in reading classes to organize it more effective?
- What are better methods to teach reading skill to pupils?
- What are the main responsibilities of teachers in conducting reading classes?
- What projects can be done to develop teaching reading abilities of language learners?

In order to answer the questions mentioned above, the researcher aims to provide not only theoretical knowledge about the subject, but also to implement several authentic materials improving teaching reading skills among students and demonstrate its effectiveness by comparing and contrasting the data gathered through the study.

BACKGROUND KNOWLEDGE

Reading is a type of speech activity aimed at the semantic perception of a graphically recorded text. Accordingly, the main purpose of reading can be considered the receipt and processing of written information.

According to A.L. Archer, (2004) the process of text recognition is instantaneous when a person has a set of lexical, phonetic and grammatical informative features. Classified by E.F. Calhoun, (1999) perception and comprehension of the text occurs simultaneously in the real process of reading, and the skills and abilities that provide the process itself are usually divided into two groups:

- perceptual processing of text (perception of graphic signs and correlation with meaning, that is, the recoding of visual signals into semantic units);
- semantic processing of the text (establishing semantic links between linguistic units of different levels and, accordingly, the content of the text, it is these skills that ensure the understanding of the text as a complete speech utterance).

Presented by D. Glenn, (2000) the level of understanding depends on the quantity and quality of words, combinations of words, sentences realized in the process of reading:

- A complete, accurate understanding of the general content and details of the text;
- A fairly accurate and complete understanding of the general content of the text with some minor inaccuracies in understanding its details;
- Incomplete, inaccurate understanding, when only the general content is clear, and many inaccuracies are found in understanding the details of the text, or when some details of the text are misunderstood;
- Fragmentary understanding, understanding of individual details of a text without understanding its general content;
- Misunderstanding of the text.

METHODOLOGY

By experimenting and comparing the data obtained, the analysis process was based on quantitative research methods. The following methods were essentially used according to the subject classes, such as the different approaches in teaching reading skill, gap-filling exercises, multiple choice tasks, interactive methods of teaching reading skill by accessible evaluation applications. They used in the study process are the incorporation of approaches to improving the competency of learners in reading skills and their use in education.

Throughout the country, language strategies interacted classrooms have the potential to include learners whose learning needs are as diverse as the contexts they come from. It is necessary to consider the work of language teaching as being relational in order to understand pedagogy and classroom practice: how teachers view their relationship with learners is informed by the contexts in which they teach and conduct their work as practitioners.

DATA COLLECTION

Before doing the study, the researcher of the current qualification paper also selected ways to collect data. There were:

- Observations;
- Questionnaires;
- Assessments and researcher's daily notes on marks.

In general, four sources were used to enforce the current analysis, which were considered to be the key sources of the research.

The researcher's qualitative approach is used in observation sheets. It is designed to observe the entire lessons in detail. In addition, needs assessment is structured to consider the needs, desires and attitudes of learners towards the teaching of group work. Pre and post-tests consist of lessons in reading skills. At the start of the teaching process, the pre-test is taken and the post-test is taken at the end of the learning process. Experimental courses were used to perform the present

research. First, before beginning to work with them and having pre and post-tests, the researcher wanted to observe some lessons from experimental courses in order to compare the findings at the end of the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The figure1 shows teachers' opinion on reading activities' effectiveness in language learning classes and 6 of them agreed this opinion while 3 of them considered they are not much interesting and effective. Only one teacher answered like they don't have any effectiveness at all.

Figure 1

Clarified from the figure, only 2 teachers' English lessons were provided with developing reading classes while 4 teachers had improving reading classes three or four times a week. 4 teachers conduct reading lessons not often but no one chose 'never' option.

It is clear from the doughnut about utilization of different reading activities instruction for improving students' reading skills, 60% (6 teachers) mentioned this method has a positive impact while 30% (3 teachers) of them considered it works

not much effectively. The last 10% (one teacher) of them thought that this method doesn't help to develop their reading abilities at all.

Figure2.

Figure3.

It is clarified from the pyramid chart, 3 teachers considered textbooks are enough for developing learners' reading skills while 7 of them disagreed on it, they thought teachers should utilize more extra materials for pupils. No one chose

'I don't know' answer.

The columns presents the data about pupils' favorite aspect of English language and 2 pupils mentioned they liked reading aspect while writing one was chosen by one learner. Most pupils like 6 of them chose listening comprehensions whereas 3 of them liked speaking abilities. 4 students chose grammar skills and likewise pronunciation aspect was also chosen by 4 pupils.

Figure4.

The pie chart reports about learners' knowledge on reading skills and 4 pupils had excellent reading base while the most 8 of them had good knowledge. However, 5 students had satisfactory qualification on reading whereas 3 students had bad degree of reading skills. But no one had too bad degree on that.

FINAL REFLECTIONS

This qualification paper developed a methodology for developing the skill of reading in a foreign language on the basis of reading instruction methods. One of the key factors is that due to their heavy workload, teachers do not have the time or resources to create appropriate materials and events and teachers' heavy workload should be reduced. As a result, their working conditions should be

changed.

The study also suggests that English teachers should be better planned. However, the available resources are insufficient to meet the demands of such a large program. Since there are so many pupils who need to learn English but not enough teachers, learners are placed in large English classes, especially in education system. As a result, English teaching is often confined to standard large-group instruction.

A reform of the current examination system is also needed. According to the results of this research paper, our public education system places much too much emphasis on grammar-based tests and as a result, English teaching practices are influenced by the skills assessed in these exams, which are primarily grammar and vocabulary skills. Other language skills such as listening, speaking, reading and writing should be prioritized. More research on how to measure learners' reading skills in a teaching reading setting should be done for this reason. It may be worth considering that large-scale summative tests should not be used as the sole criteria for selecting and placing students for future education. Formative exams, on the other hand, should be integrated into English education. Students' reading abilities can be better reflected in selection and placement instruments from this viewpoint. Similarly, such a reform will improve both teachers' and learners' incentive to teach and learn reading through text and tasks.

The results of this study confirmed that English teachers believe their concerns, questions and English teaching problems in EFL contexts are not adequately discussed. The study's participants discussed the drawbacks of teaching English as a foreign language. As a result, more emphasis should be placed on research that focuses on the unique characteristics of English learning and teaching in EFL settings.

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